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THE IMPACTS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES FOR ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

School physical education is characterized by classes made up of activities that involve various bodily practices and experiences. The place of bodily practices in the educational process is of the utmost importance, as they present yet another possibility for reading the world. Through body practices, young people can portray the world in which they live, produce and reproduce their values, beliefs, feelings, concepts and prejudices. Through bodily practices, young people and adolescents can construct their place of speech in cultural and social dynamics. The pandemic caused by Covid-19 has led physical education teachers to adapt their content to the new reality. Thus, in addition to the challenges present in face-to-face classes, the return to schools has also brought significant transformations in the educational sphere.